

Valorization of grape pomace (cv. *Muscat*) for development of functional cookies

Radhika Theagarajan, Lavanya MN, Sayantani Dutta, Moses JA and Anandharamakrishnan C*
Indian Institute of Food Processing Technology (IIFPT), Thanjavur 613005, India

Summary

Fruit juice industries and wineries generate considerable amounts of grape pomace as waste from fresh grapes. At present there is no defined utilization of the pomace generated, thereby increasing the bioburden. However, the pomace is a nutritional asset and consists of many salutary benefits. This study on pomace powder of grapes of cv. *Muscat* revealed stable physiochemical properties and considerable antioxidant potential. The pomace was supplemented into cookies as a nutraceutical, to develop a functional snack. Cookies showed best antioxidant activity and appreciable shelf life when the pomace was administered at 6% w/w in the dough. These cookies had total phenol content at 4.03 ± 0.37 mg GAE/g, and total anthocyanin content at 38.30 ± 1.80 mg/100 g. The said cookies also had highest physicochemical stability and sensory acceptance. The present endeavor illustrated a scheme for utilization of by products of agro processing industries in developing salubrious shelf stable food products, minimizing agro waste.

Keywords: Grape pomace, waste valorization, phenols, cookies, functional properties

*Corresponding author

Email: anandharamakrishnan@iifpt.edu.in

Introduction

Grapes (*Vitis vinifera*) are one of the most cultivated and consumed fruits in the world. The global annual production of grapes in the recent past was about 60 million tons (Rondeau *et al.*, 2013), providing evidence for its bulk production in the world. The importance of grapes has increased recently, especially after research has revealed that they are rich in antioxidants and dietary fiber (Burin *et al.*, 2014), as well as polyphenolic phytochemical (Makris & Kefalas, 2013). It is noteworthy that the major quantum of grapes produced in the world are used for wine production (FAOSTAT, 2013). The by-products, produced post juice extraction from grapes, constituting about 20% are used in deriving grape pomace (Laufenberg *et al.*, 2003). Grape pomace is basically the residue obtained post pressing of the grapes, during preparation of juice and/or wine (Karnopp *et al.*, 2015). The pomace consists of small pieces of stalks, skin, seed, and some pulp from the fruit. Generally, grape pomace is used to produce grape seed oil and food colours (García Lomillo & González SanJosé, 2017).

It is worth mentioning that polyphenols are abundant in grape pomace and contribute to its antioxidant activity (Negro *et al.*, 2003). These phytochemicals comprise chiefly of family of flavonols, such as catechins, that have inhibitory effects on *in vitro* platelet reactivity and are able to avert risks of cardio vascular diseases (Quiñones *et al.*, 2013). These findings corroborate the importance of grape pomace as a potential source of nutraceuticals.

The objective of this study was to develop a value-added food product administered with grape pomace as a nutraceutical-rich supplement. For the said aim, cookies were chosen to be the model food product. Previously, value addition to this popular snack has been done by many authors, such as with antioxidant-rich black pepper and cardamom extracts (Dutta *et al.*, 2017), and nutrient-rich coconut copra (Ghosh *et al.*, 2017). Although there are many authors who have

worked on utilization of grape pomace in developing cookies, the cultivar, pomace ingredients and methods employed in this study are unique, to the best of our knowledge. The similarities and/or differences from other researches on grape pomace cookies have nevertheless been highlighted in the course of the present report.

The present study envisages characterizing the physicochemical aspects of grape pomace and subsequently designing ‘grape pomace cookies’. These cookies have been characterized in terms of their nutritional, sensory and antioxidant properties, along with assessment of their shelf life. The intent was to create a nutraceutical-rich snack using industrial waste.

Materials and methods

Materials

Fresh, ripe red grapes (*Vitis vinifera*) cv. *Muscat* (for details please refer Supplementary file) grown in Tamil Nadu, India were purchased from farmers cultivating the variety in the state. Reagents and standards were procured from Himedia, India. All chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade. For the preparation of cookies, refined flour, butter, sugar powder and vanilla essence were procured from a local supermarket at Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu.

Preparation of pomace

The grapes were cleaned, pressed to release the juice, and the pomace was separated from the pulp; akin industrial waste. The detailed process of preparation of pomace powder has been discussed in Supplementary file.

Proximate composition of pomace powder

Determination of moisture, fat, protein, ash, and carbohydrate contents of grape pomace powder were performed according to the standard methods (AOAC, 2016).

Phytochemical properties of pomace powder

Extraction of bioactive components from pomace powder

For extraction of phytochemical properties from grape pomace, it was stirred with distilled water at 60°C (solute/solvent ratio of 1:10 m/v) for 3 h. Then the mixture was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min. and the resulting supernatant was stored at $-18\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ until used (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2015).

Total phenolic content

Total phenolic content in the extract was estimated using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent according to the method reported by previous researchers (Jayaprakasha & Rao, 2000), with few modifications. A sample (0.2 ml) was mixed with 1.0 ml of a 10X diluted Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 0.8 ml of 7.5% Na_2CO_3 solution. Post mixing, the sample was stored at room temperature in dark for 30 min, and thereafter the absorbance was measured at 765 nm in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UV-1800, Shimadzu, Japan). The result of total phenolic content was expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE)/g dry matter (DM) of grape pomace.

Total anthocyanin content

The total anthocyanin content (TAC) in pomace powder was estimated in accordance with the method described erstwhile (Giusti & Wrolstad, 2001). For this assay, the sample was first homogenized with acid and ethanol and kept for 24 h at -4°C . Then the samples were filtered and their absorbance was read in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer at 510 and 700 nm, respectively.

Preparation of grape pomace incorporated cookies

Post pomace characterization, cookies were prepared using blends of refined wheat flour and grape pomace powder, in ratios of 100:0, 98:2, 96:4, 94:6, 92:8 w/w. Initial trials of cookies were prepared with concentration between 10% to 50% of flour. Cookies with 10% flour exhibited good sensory properties; whereas rest combinations showed lower acceptability, and so further combinations were studied between 2%-10% of flour.

These cookies were prepared with fixed quantities of sugar powder (50 g), shortening (45 g), vanilla essence (0.3 g) in each variant. Subsequently, flour and pomace were added, the mass kneaded, and the cookie dough was prepared. Then the dough was sheeted to 10 mm thickness and cut into circular shapes (3 cm) using a cutter. The raw cookies were then placed on a butter monolayered metallic tray. They were baked in a baking oven (Lab Tech, India) pre-heated to 160°C for 12 min. Post baking, the cookies were cooled to ambient temperature and packed in air-tight metalized polyester pouches and stored until further analyses, at 23±2°C. Control cookies (without addition of pomace) were also prepared in the same way.

Physicochemical properties of cookies

Physical characteristics

Control cookies and pomace incorporated cookies (at 2%, 4%, 6% and 8%, w/w of flour) were analyzed for their physical properties such as weight, diameter (D), thickness (T) and spread ratio (D/T). Five cookies were analyzed in a set for the above parameters.

Water activity (a_w)

Water activity of cookies was recorded using a water activity meter (AQUALAB 4TE, USA) at $24\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. It measured the amount of viable water molecules present in the food system. Lesser the water activity, lower will be possibility of microbial growth.

Proximate composition

Determination of moisture, fat, protein, ash, and carbohydrate contents of pomace incorporated cookies were conducted according to the standard methods (AOAC, 2012). The value of energy could be calculated by summation of the calories obtained from carbohydrates, proteins and lipids, using the conversion factors 4 kcal/g, 4 kcal/g, and 9 kcal/g respectively; provided by the proximate values, as described (Frery *et al.*, 2005).

Sensory analysis of the cookies

Sensory perceptions of grape pomace incorporated and control cookies were assessed by semi-trained panel of 30 panelists comprising of research scholars and technical staff of the department. The assessment was on a 9-point hedonic scale, conducted between 10 am - 12 noon in the research laboratory of the institute. This was as per the method of sensory evaluation described by Ranganna (Ranganna, 1986). Sensory analysis was carried out for attributes of overall appearance, colour, odour, texture, taste and after taste. The panelists were also provided drinking water to clean the palate, and crackers to avoid flavour carry over, in between consecutive samples. For each sample, mean score for each attribute by each panelist was recorded, and then the overall mean score of each attribute for a given sample was calculated.

Phytochemical assay of cookies

Total phenolic content

Total phenolic content of cookies was estimated using the Folin-Ciocalteu method as earlier described (Gat & Ananthanarayan, 2015). For each sample, three replicate assays were performed. The results of total phenolic content were expressed as mg GAE/ g of cookies (dry basis).

Shelf life of cookies

The storability of cookies was studied for 60 days and the attributes of texture (fracturability and hardness) and peroxide value (PV) were monitored. Analyses were done on days 0, 30 and 60.

To evaluate the textural attributes of cookies such as hardness and fracturability (as fracture force), Texture Analyzer (TA-XT2i, Stable Micro systems, UK.) was used. During examination, a 3-point bending test of the sample was conducted, using a 3-point bending rig with a trigger force 25 g and a load cell 50 kg. The distance between the two bottom supports of texture analyzer was maintained at 50 mm. The probe was calibrated and the cookie sample was placed on the two beams. As the probe came in contact with the cookie, the cookie fractured due to the applied force. This fracture force, i.e., the hardness value was noted, while the peak force (g) at breaking point represented the fracturability of the cookie (Arifin *et al.*, 2010).

The oxidative stability calculation was based on PV following the method described earlier (Muresan *et al.*, 2010). Fat was extracted from the cookies by Soxhlet method. The collected oil (30 to 40 mg) was added with 9.8 ml of chloroform/methanol (7:3 v/v), 50 µl of ammonium thiocyanate and ferrous chloride solution. This mixture of solution was vortexed for 5 min at room temperature and kept in the dark. After 5 min, the absorbance was measured at 500 nm by UV-Vis spectrophotometer. PV calculated by using Fe (III) standard curve as previously described (Muresan *et al.*, 2010):

$$PV (mEq O_2/kg fat) = \frac{Abs}{55.84 \times w} \times \frac{1}{b} \quad (1)$$

Where, 'w' is the weight of the oil, Abs is absorbance, b is the slope of the Fe (III) standard curve and 55.84 is the atomic weight of Fe (III).

Statistical analyses

All the experiments were performed in triplicate and the data were expressed as mean \pm SD of three independent experiments. One-way ANOVA was conducted on the means to assess significant difference in the data, at $p \leq 0.05$, using SPSS software (IBM Inc., USA).

Results and discussion

Proximate analysis of pomace powder

The grape pomace powder had 5.50% moisture (dry weight). Total protein content of pomace powder was estimated to be 5.57%, ash content was 3.86% and the fiber content of pomace was 1.03%.

The lipid profile of the grape pomace has previously revealed 8.41% total fats, with about 90% monounsaturated fatty acids, that reportedly protect human cardiovascular system (Rockenbach *et al.*, 2011). The pomace was also rich in carbohydrates (74.96%). Similar values were reported by Sousa *et al.* (2014) for the grape variety *Benitaka*.

Phytochemical properties of pomace powder

Antioxidant activity

The total phenolic content of grape pomace was found to be 280.6 ± 3 mg GAE/g of dry weight of grape pomace. Similar values (261 to 365 mg/100g) were also obtained by Pastrana-Bonilla *et al.* who worked with *Muscadine* grape variety (Pastrana-Bonilla *et al.*, 2003).

Total anthocyanin content

Anthocyanin is present in grape skin, and their content ranges from 30 - 750 mg/100 g, depending upon the variety of the grapes (Rockenbach *et al.*, 2011). In the current study, anthocyanin content was found to be 38.30 ± 1.80 mg/100 g of grape pomace. Notably, difference in values of phytochemical potency is often induced due to the difference in cultivar, cultivation method, climatic conditions of growth, physicochemical factors such as pH and temperature and the bioactive extraction method.

Physical characteristics of grape pomace cookies

The appearance of cookies (post baking) that were incorporated with different concentration of grape pomace has been shown in Fig. 1. The picture shows the difference in colour among different cookies. The cookies particularly became darker as the content of pomace increased. This observation was congruent with previous researchers who have reported that incorporation of grape pomace produces a darker shade in the cookies, compared to control cookies (Canett *et al.*, 2004).

The basic characteristics of cookies were also determined by calculating its weight, diameter, thickness, spread ratio, spread factor and water activity values (Table 1). Significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) were found between control and test samples for all the above mentioned parameters. From the result of spread ratio it can be concluded that incorporation of grape pomace powder improved the baking quality of the cookies. Incorporation of grape pomace into cookies resulted in an increased water activity from 0.3 to 0.42. This observation could be owing to the fact that grape pomace powder had inherent internal moisture that could have increased the water activity of cookies. The values, however, were well within permissible limits for safe application (0.3-0.4), wherein there is no microbial growth (Bussiere & Serpelloni, 1985).

Proximate analysis of cookies

The results of proximate analysis for pomace incorporated cookies have represented significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) in moisture content of the control and grape pomace incorporated cookies (Table 2). The incorporation of pomace powder into cookies showed decreased moisture content compared to control. Earlier, Manley has stated that moisture content in cookies could vary between 2.5-3.0% (Manley, 2011), attesting the present find. From the results it is clear that incorporation of pomace powder decreased the moisture content of the cookies that eventually increased the shelf life of the product.

Protein content of the cookies showed a significant difference between the control and test samples. This indicates that grape pomace accorded to increased protein content in the cookies. All test samples showed higher fat content compared to control cookies. Fat has been reported to be an important component in influencing the flavor, texture and appearance of cookies (Maache-Rezzoug *et al.*, 1998).

Further, ash content indicates the amount of minerals present in a food. In this study, there was a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) between ashes of control and test samples, which reflects increased mineral content of pomace incorporated cookies. Significant difference in terms of carbohydrate content was also recorded between control and pomace cookies. Also, an increased energy value was obtained for grape pomace cookies (Table 2).

Sensory evaluation of cookies

The sensory analysis data has been presented in Fig. 2. Appearance and colour were reportedly the major parameters that played important roles in determining the preference by the panel. A significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) was found in colour of control cookies and pomace cookies, with

an increase in the dark shade in the colour of pomace incorporated cookies. Other sensory parameters such as taste, after taste, flavor, and texture also showed significant difference compared with control cookies. Owing to a bitter taste, as the percentage grape pomace increased, overall acceptance of the cookies reduced.

Among four different concentrations, 4% and 6% showed good acceptability, and maximum scores were allotted to 4% and 6% grape pomace incorporated cookies. The panelists stated that 8% pomace cookies had a harder texture and bitter taste; while, in 2% pomace cookies, the taste was indifferent from control cookies (unsuitable to be called pomace-cookie). These sample descriptions were separately recorded from panelists. A decrement of sensory acceptability at higher percentage of grape pomace (10%) has also been observed by other authors (Acun & Gül, 2013). In another study, researchers have claimed that addition of pomace up to 15% is sensorially acceptable, with pomace replacing wheat flour in the dough (Kuchtová *et al.*, 2016). These observations suggest possible effects of cultivars and growth conditions of grapes on pomace quality and consequently, variable limits for sensory acceptance of pomace cookies. Hence, for next set of analyses, cookies with 4% and 6% pomace were selected.

Total phenol content of grape pomace cookies

The sample with 6% pomace showed significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) content of total phenols (4.03 ± 0.37 mg GAE/g) than 4% pomace (3.42 ± 0.30 mg GAE/g) and control cookies (3.41 ± 0.28 mg GAE/g). Increment in antioxidant activity and total phenol content in cookies incorporated with grape pomace has been also reported by Karnopp *et al.* (Karnopp *et al.*, 2015). The nutraceuticals benefits of pomace supplementation to food products has also been discussed at length by a review in the recent past, focusing on healthfulness of wine-pomace, establishing the importance of such a supplementation (García-Lomillo & González-SanJosé, 2017).

Shelf life study of grape pomace cookies

For storability, there was a significant difference in texture between test and control cookies, during the test period. The pomace cookies retained their textural attributes much better than the control set (Figs. 3a and 3b). The hardness value also serves as a benchmark for freshness, as well as scrumptiousness of cookies. Maintaining the hardness in cookies is an essential prerequisite, to avoid breakage during transport. Slade *et al.* have correlated fracturing ability to the level of collapse during end stages of baking (Slade *et al.*, 1993). During the cooling phase, post-baking, starch and proteins bind together (solidify), rendering cookies to be firm. Also, after cooling, sugar tends to re-crystallize at the cookie's crust, especially during storage, providing the necessary crispiness in texture of cookies (Hoseney & Rogers, 1994). Retention of hardness in cookies with pomace addition could be due to enhanced antioxidant effect as well, limiting peroxidation. Such an opinion has been made by Karnopp *et al.* as well (Karnopp *et al.*, 2015).

Fat content also plays a vital role in storability of food products, since it governs lipid peroxidation that has pronounced effect in fatty foods when stored (Maache-Rezzoug *et al.*, 1998). Oxidative stability was analyzed based on PV that indicates the extent of oxidation and formation of primary oxidation products, with storage (Fig. 3c). PV was found to significantly increase in cookies on the 60th day of storage. Addition of butter (fat) in cookies is one of causes for peroxidation, and influences the keeping quality of the cookies. When compared with control cookies, addition of grape pomace powder increased the antioxidant activity, thereby averting rancidity.

Although generation of peroxides in cookies during storage did occur, the lead in shelf stability of pomace cookies over control cookies was still significant. This find provided clear evidence for incorporating of grape pomace cookies for added nutritional benefits, sensory

appeal and shelf life. Cookies with 6% grape pomace showed lowest PV; hence, these cookies were most shelf stable during the course of the study. A low moisture content in cookies in general probably also helped in improving stability (Table 2). We therefore conclude that grape pomace should be administered to cookie dough at 6% (w/w), for preparing shelf stable (at least 60 days) nutraceutical-rich functional cookies.

Conclusion

In the present study, antioxidant-rich grape pomace powder was used as a nutraceutical at different concentrations, to develop functional cookies. Interestingly, the figure achieved of 5.87% pomace being produced from a kg of fresh grapes itself signifies the need for this study. This functional cookie (6% pomace, w/w) has been found to have enhanced taste along with undergoing low oxidation, increased antioxidant property (such as total phenols) and having appreciable shelf life. More food applications of this valuable bioresource are warranted for versatile utilities of the same as a food supplement, for enhanced use in value addition to existing food products.

Acknowledgment

Authors would like to thank Department of Biotechnology, Government of India for providing financial assistance.

Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

References

Acun, S. & Gül, H. (2013). Effects of grape pomace and grape seed flours on cookie quality. *Quality Assurance and Safety of Crops & Foods*, **6**, 81-88.

- AOAC International (2016) Official methods of analysis, 20th edn. (On-line). AOAC International, Rockville, MD
- Arifin, N., Peng, K. S., Long, K., Ping, T. C., Affandi Yusoff, M. S., Nor Aini, I. & Ming, L. O. (2010). Relationship between textural properties and sensory qualities of cookies made from medium-and long-chain triacylglycerol-enriched margarines. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, **90**, 943-948.
- Burin, V. M., Ferreira-Lima, N. E., Panceri, C. P. & Bordignon-Luiz, M. T. (2014). Bioactive compounds and antioxidant activity of *Vitis vinifera* and *Vitis labrusca* grapes: evaluation of different extraction methods. *Microchemical Journal*, **114**, 155-163.
- Bussiere, G. & Serpelloni, M. (1985). Confectionery and water activity determination of a w by calculation. In: Properties of Water in Foods. Pp. 627-645. Springer.
- Canett, R. R., Ledesma, A. O., Robles, R. S., Morales, R. C., Leon-Martinez, L. & León-Gálvez, R. (2004). Characterization of cookies made with deseeded grape pomace. *Archivos Latinoamericanos de nutricion*, **54**, 93-99.
- Carr, R. L. (1965). Evaluating flow properties of solids. *Chemical Engineering*, **18**, 163-168.
- Dutta, S., Bhattacharjee, P. & Bhattacharyya, N. (2017). Assessment of shelf lives of black pepper and small cardamom cookies by metal oxide-based electronic nose using spoilage index. *Food and Bioprocess Technology*, **10**, 2023-2033.
- FAOSTAT, D. (2013). Food and agriculture organization of the United Nations. Statistical database.
- Frary, C. D., Johnson, R. K. & Wang, M. Q. (2005). Food sources and intakes of caffeine in the diets of persons in the United States. *Journal of the American Dietetic Association*, **105**, 110-113.

- García-Lomillo, J. & González-SanJosé, M. L. (2017). Applications of wine pomace in the food industry: approaches and functions. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, **16**, 3-22.
- García Lomillo, J. & González SanJosé, M. L. (2017). Applications of wine pomace in the food industry: approaches and functions. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, **16**, 3-22.
- Gat, Y. & Ananthanarayan, L. (2015). Effect of extrusion process parameters and pregelatinized rice flour on physicochemical properties of ready-to-eat expanded snacks. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, **52**, 2634-2645.
- Ghosh, P. K., Bhattacharjee, P. & Poddar-Sarkar, M. (2017b). Reduction of lauric acid in coconut copra by supercritical carbon dioxide extraction: Process optimization and design of functional cookies using the lauric acid-lean copra meal. *Journal of Food Process Engineering*, **40**, e12501.
- Giusti, M. M. & Wrolstad, R. E. (2001). Characterization and measurement of anthocyanins by UV-Visible spectroscopy. *Current Protocols in Food Analytical Chemistry*, <https://doi.org/10.1002/0471142913.faf0102s00>.
- Hoseney, R. & Rogers, D. (1994). Mechanism of sugar functionality in cookies. Pp. 203-225. New York, Chapman & Hall.
- Igathinathane, C., Womac, A. & Sokhansanj, S. (2010). Corn stalk orientation effect on mechanical cutting. *Biosystems engineering*, **107**, 97-106.
- Jayaprakasha, G. K. & Rao, L. J. (2000). Phenolic constituents from the lichen *Parmotrema stippeum* (Nyl.) Hale and their antioxidant activity. *Zeitschrift für Naturforschung C*, **55**, 1018-1022.

- Karnopp, A. R., Figueroa, A. M., Los, P. R., Teles, J. C., Simões, D. R. S., Barana, A. C., Kubiaki, F. T., OLIVEIRA, J. G. B. d. & Granato, D. (2015). Effects of whole-wheat flour and bordeaux grape pomace (*Vitis labrusca* L.) on the sensory, physicochemical and functional properties of cookies. *Food Science and Technology*, **35**, 750-756.
- Kuchtová, V., Karovičová, J., Kohajdová, Z., Minarovičová, L. & Kimličková, V. (2016). Effects of white grape preparation on sensory quality of cookies. *Acta Chimica Slovaca*, **9**, 84-88.
- Laufenberg, G., Kunz, B. & Nystroem, M. (2003). Transformation of vegetable waste into value added products::(A) the upgrading concept;(B) practical implementations. *Bioresource Technology*, **87**, 167-198.
- Maache-Rezzoug, Z., Bouvier, J.-M., Allaf, K. & Patras, C. (1998). Effect of principal ingredients on rheological behaviour of biscuit dough and on quality of biscuits. *Journal of Food Engineering*, **35**, 23-42.
- Makris, D. & Kefalas, P. (2013). Characterization of polyphenolic phytochemicals in red grape pomace. *International Journal of Waste Resources*, **126**, DOI: 10.4172/2252-5211.1000126.
- Manley, D. (2011). *Manley's Technology of Biscuits, Crackers and Cookies*. Elsevier.
- Muresan, V., Muste, S., Racola, E., Semeniuc, C. A., Man, S. & Chirichu, C. (2010). Determination of peroxide value in sunflower halva using a spectrophotometric method. *Bulletin of University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca. Agriculture*, **67**.
- Negro, C., Tommasi, L. & Miceli, A. (2003). Phenolic compounds and antioxidant activity from red grape marc extracts. *Bioresource Technology*, **87**, 41-44.

- Pastrana-Bonilla, E., Akoh, C. C., Sellappan, S. & Krewer, G. (2003). Phenolic content and antioxidant capacity of muscadine grapes. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, **51**, 5497-5503.
- Quiñones, M., Miguel, M. & Aleixandre, A. (2013). Beneficial effects of polyphenols on cardiovascular disease. *Pharmacological Research*, **68**, 125-131.
- Ranganna, S. (1986). Handbook of Analysis and Quality Control for Fruit and Vegetable Products. Tata McGraw-Hill Education.
- Ribeiro, L., Ribani, R., Francisco, T., Soares, A., Pontarolo, R. & Haminiuk, C. (2015). Profile of bioactive compounds from grape pomace (*Vitis vinifera* and *Vitis labrusca*) by spectrophotometric, chromatographic and spectral analyses. *Journal of Chromatography B*, **1007**, 72-80.
- Rockenbach, I. I., Gonzaga, L. V., Rizelio, V. M., Gonçalves, A. E. d. S. S., Genovese, M. I. & Fett, R. (2011). Phenolic compounds and antioxidant activity of seed and skin extracts of red grape (*Vitis vinifera* and *Vitis labrusca*) pomace from Brazilian winemaking. *Food Research International*, **44**, 897-901.
- Rondeau, P., Gambier, F., Jolibert, F. & Brosse, N. (2013). Compositions and chemical variability of grape pomaces from French vineyard. *Industrial Crops and Products*, **43**, 251-254.
- Slade, L., Levine, H., Ievolella, J. & Wang, M. (1993). The glassy state phenomenon in applications for the food industry: application of the food polymer science approach to structure–function relationships of sucrose in cookie and cracker systems. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, **63**, 133-176.

Sousa, E. C., Uchôa-Thomaz, A. M. A., Carioca, J. O. B., Morais, S. M. d., Lima, A. d., Martins, C. G., Alexandrino, C. D., Ferreira, P. A. T., Rodrigues, A. L. M. & Rodrigues, S. P. (2014). Chemical composition and bioactive compounds of grape pomace (*Vitis vinifera* L.), Benitaka variety, grown in the semiarid region of northeast Brazil. *Food Science and Technology*, **34**, 135-142.

Figure

Fig 1. Appearance of cookies at different concentrations of grape pomace.

Fig 2. Sensory analysis of cookies.

Fig 3. Storage studies of cookies with respect to textural attributes of (a) fracturability, (b) hardness; and lipid peroxidation by (c) peroxide value.

Tables:

Table 1 Physical properties of cookies

Physical Parameters	Control	% Grape pomace incorporated			
		2%	4%	6%	8%
Weight (g)	6.45±0.64 ^a	7.41±0.40 ^a	5.05±0.89 ^b	6.23±0.56 ^a	5.87±0.48 ^b
Diameter (D) (mm)	37.44±3.12 ^a	37.46±2.86 ^a	40.63±3.94 ^a	38.30±3.63 ^a	40.26±3.70 ^a
Thickness (T) (mm)	9.28±1.59 ^a	8.35±0.91 ^a	7.80±1.01 ^a	6.93±0.24 ^b	7.19±0.67 ^a
Spread ratio (D/T)	4.03 ^a	4.52 ^a	5.20 ^a	5.52 ^a	5.59 ^a
Spread factor	-	112.24 ^a	129.18 ^a	137.07 ^a	138.88 ^a
Water activity (a _w)	0.37±0.03 ^a	0.30±0.02 ^a	0.42±0.04 ^a	0.39±0.03 ^a	0.41±0.04 ^a

Baking quality values of cookies are mean ± SD of three independent experimental runs
Different letters in row represent significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 2 Proximate analyses of cookies

Sample	Moisture (% dry basis)	Ash (% dry basis)	Fat (% dry basis)	Protein (% dry basis)	Fiber (% dry basis)	Carbohydrate (% dry basis)	Energy (Kcal)
Control	4.63±0.41 ^a	0.53±0.03 ^a	7.27±0.87 ^a	5.30±0.54 ^a	1.74±0.14 ^a	80.50±3.68 ^a	408.63±18.21 ^a
2%	2.64±0.30 ^b	0.56±0.06 ^a	6.51±0.59 ^a	4.27±0.33 ^b	2.13±0.25 ^b	83.86±4.91 ^a	419.57±12.26 ^a
4%	3.36±0.45 ^c	0.43±0.03 ^b	12.49±1.56 ^c	4.79±0.46 ^b	1.84±0.12 ^a	77.03±2.58 ^a	439.69±16.08 ^a
6%	2.34±0.20 ^b	0.66±0.04 ^c	12.07±1.00 ^c	5.20±0.58 ^a	1.83±0.14 ^a	77.87±1.88 ^a	440.97±16.24 ^a
8%	3.65±0.32 ^c	0.47±0.05 ^b	13.85±1.13 ^c	6.26±0.44 ^c	2.52±0.18 ^c	73.23±2.84 ^a	442.62±19.58 ^a

Proximate compositions the cookies are mean ± SD of three independent experimental runs

Different letters in column represent significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$

%GP= % Grape pomace incorporated in cookies